

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE IMAGINATION OF PRIMARY STUDENTS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15475240>

Abstract: This article provides detailed ideas on the development of creative imagination of primary school students.

Keywords: education, upbringing, social consciousness, dedication, development, creativity, ability, imagination, knowledge, potential, creativity.

Introduction. The current modern education system is being formed in accordance with the socio-economic needs of society. Raising a new generation of fully developed, independent thinkers, with a creative outlook has become one of the urgent tasks of today. In this sense, the primary education stage is an important stage when the first worldview, intellectual activity and creative abilities of our child begin to form.

The development of creative imagination in primary school students is of great importance for their independent and effective activity in the future educational process. Creative imagination forms the child's ability to create new ideas, an unconventional approach to reality, and observation. At the same time, each teacher has the task of awakening children's creative thinking through various methodological approaches and pedagogical means.

In this regard, studying the issue of developing creative imagination in primary school students as a pedagogical problem and identifying effective methods and ways in this regard is gaining relevance today.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in improving the system of continuous education, improving the quality and efficiency of education, the level and potential of developing creative imagination of primary school students, along with material factors, are also of great importance. The primary education system has a special place in creating the necessary conditions for the development of children's creative imagination and the ability to function in accordance with the requirements of the time.

Literature review. Today, the main goal of developing the creative imagination of elementary school students is to make the young generation mature in all respects, well-rounded people necessary for the development of our society. A perfect person embodies spiritual and physical maturity. In order to develop the creative imagination of students, folklore, folk tales, stories, legends, children's encyclopedias, and children's books reflecting pictorial expression play a key role. In addition, the legacy of Eastern thinkers, poems and ghazals, examples of artistic creations serve as a program. If we rely on the socio-political, philosophical and educational views of such scholars as Ahmad Yassawi, Bahauddin Naqshbandi, Al-Bukhari, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Abulkasim Firdawsi, Amur Temur, Alisher Navoi, and Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur, the work on developing the creative imagination of students will be further improved.

The development of the creative imagination of primary school students is a pedagogical problem that is the basis of the educational process, requires constant attention and care, and does not lose its relevance.

When studying the history of the development of educational methods in Central Asia, we can see that various methods have been used in practice in education. In particular, Abu Ali ibn Sino, in his work "Tadbir al-Manzil", says that young children should be raised in a certain order from birth to adulthood. He considers group teaching to be preferable to individual teaching, and writes about the advantages of this method: "Students feel a thirst for knowledge during their studies and upbringing. When students are together, they always talk to each other, thereby developing their imagination and speech" [1].

The problems of educating a creative person had a special place in the researches of Jan Amos Comenius, who emphasized that the sensory organs of a person, which help to study existence, occupy a leading place in the cognitive system, described the empirical, scientific and practical stages in the development of cognitive processes, the nature of consciousness and intuition, which are the main sources of cognition [2].

K. D. Ushinsky was one of the first to establish the mechanism of development of creativity, which consists in the development of qualities of imagination, thinking and will. He notes the need to cultivate confidence and determination in the ideas that are being formed in the process of students' development of creative qualities [3].

In the researches of the pedagogic scientists S. Nishonova, M. Kuronov, the concepts of raising a mature generation and forming a mature personality were created based on the formation of the spiritual and moral consciousness of the student [4].

Discussion. At the same time, tasks aimed at the creative development of the child have been identified in psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature, but they are not sufficiently covered in the education system, and practical instructions have not been developed. The pedagogical conditions necessary for the development of students' creative imagination in the classroom have not been identified.

In order to reveal the conceptual and terminological apparatus of the study, an attempt was made to determine how creativity is understood in psychological and pedagogical research, how it is related to creativity and creativity.

In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" - "creativity" is defined as creative activity, creative labor associated with creativity, creativity. In pedagogical dictionaries, "creativity" is defined as an activity that produces something new based on the reorganization of experience, the formation of a combination of new knowledge and skills.

Creativity has different degrees. Creativity at one level is characterized by the application of existing knowledge, while at another level it is considered a new approach to changing the usual view of objects or areas of knowledge.

In addition, we turned to the psychological dictionary to understand creative imagination. The concept of "imagination" is defined as follows: "Imagination is the process of remembering objects and events, situations, images of reality, as well as creative imagination. It also manifests itself in the form of memory. If perception reflects the present moment, imagination embodies both the past and the future, acquiring a generalized nature." Imagination is of great importance in the acquisition of knowledge and professional skills. Imagination has both a general, private and social nature. Social imagination reflects universal and national customs, rituals, traditions and values [5].

In the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” it is defined as “Imagination is to think, imagine, bring to mind, embody in thought and mind” [109].

Over the years, professors Sh.S.Sharipov, Ch.T.Shokirova, N.G.Alovutdinova, M.Abdullaeva, A.R.Khamroev, B.R.Adizov, Z.T.Nishanova have conducted a number of studies on the issues of creativity and creative work.

Sh.S.Sharipov in his doctoral dissertation “Theory and Practice of Ensuring the Integrity of Students' Professional Creativity” emphasizes that “two interrelated tasks should be taken into account when organizing students' creative activities. The first of them is determined by the development of independent thinking in students' creative activities, their aspiration to acquire knowledge, and the formation of a scientific worldview, and the second is by teaching them to independently apply the acquired knowledge in education and practical activities.” Based on the tasks mentioned by Sh.S. Sharipov, he came to the conclusion that it is possible to organize not only the professional creativity of students, but also the process of creative activity of children from an early age, by enriching their imagination during primary school, developing their mental skills, finding different solutions to achieve their goals, and getting used to the skills of making the right decisions. In our study, some of the features of directing students to the profession were mentioned in some of the activities aimed at developing the creative imagination of elementary school students.

In conclusion, development of students' creative imagination at the primary education stage is not only an important part of the educational process, but also one of the main factors that serve to form a person who can think creatively and make independent decisions in the future.

Conclusion. The role of the teacher in this direction is invaluable, and his pedagogical skills, methodological knowledge and innovative approaches play a decisive role in stimulating creative activity in the minds of children. The effective use of interactive methods, creative tasks, role-playing games and dialogue-oriented exercises in the learning process expands the scope of children's thinking and enriches the world of imagination.

Therefore, an in-depth study of the issue of developing the creative imagination of primary school students and improving practical methods and tools remains one of the important pedagogical tasks facing the current education system.

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